

Bridging the AI Gap: Validating Student Preference for Dialogic, Co-Agency, and Ethical Learning in Indonesia

***Udan Kusmawaan**

Chemistry Education Department, Universitas Terbuka, Indonesia

<https://orcid.org/0000-0001-7550-9029>

*Corresponding author email address: Email: udan@ecampus.ut.ac.id

Ridi Ferdiana

Electrical and Information Engineering Department, Universitas Gadjah Mada, Indonesia

<https://orcid.org/0000-0001-9961-5205>

Dodi Sukmayadi

Physics Education Department, Universitas Terbuka, Indonesia

<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-2751-3098>

Zulfikri Anas

Elementary Teacher Education Department, Universitas Terbuka, Indonesia

<https://orcid.org/0009-0001-3117-9790>

Sukma Wahyu Wijayanti

Chemistry Education Department, Universitas Terbuka, Indonesia

<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2710-4486>

Mery Noviyanti

Mathematics Education Department, Universitas Terbuka, Indonesia

<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-4729-7959>

Abstract

Background: The rapid diffusion of Artificial Intelligence (AI) shifts essential student competencies from routine recall toward higher-order skills such as dialogue, co-agency, ethical judgment, and real-world problem-solving. Educational systems require empirical evidence to determine whether learners prefer and are ready for these transformed environments.

Objective: This study examines the extent of Indonesian upper-secondary students' preferences for Post-School Pedagogy (PSP)—specifically dialogic learning, co-agency, community-connected projects, authentic evidence, and ethical AI—while profiling differences across regional and demographic subgroups.

Methodology: A cross-sectional survey was conducted among 827 Grade 11 and 12 students across 19 Indonesian provinces (31.9% in West, 31.7% in Central, 36.4% in East). Preferences were measured using 10 items on a 7-point desirability scale. Analytical techniques included

Welch-robust ANOVA with Holm post hoc tests, Welch t-tests (Hedges' g), OLS (HC3) regression, and mixed-effects models with province-level random intercepts.

Results: Students demonstrated a strong overall preference for PSP ($M = 5.22$, $SD = 0.82$). Regional analysis revealed a significant gradient: West (5.31) > Central (5.22) > East (5.10). Specifically, the West–East difference was statistically significant ($\Delta = 0.21$, $p < .001$, $g = 0.24$). While female students and those in urban/peri-urban areas showed slightly higher preferences, other subgroup effects were trivial. Low between-province variance ($ICC = 0.03$) suggests that most preference variance is attributable to the individual student level.

Conclusion: Indonesian students express a clear preference for PSP features, with only minor regional and subgroup disparities. The findings support a national shift toward more interactive and agency-focused learning models.

Unique Contribution: This study provides interdisciplinary evidence that students actively seek dialogic, co-designed, and ethically AI-enabled learning. It bridges educational psychology, the sociology of education, and communication to validate student readiness for AI-driven pedagogical shifts.

Key Recommendation: Policy should prioritise scaling PSP through teacher professional development in dialogic facilitation, structured co-design, and community partnerships. Implementation must prioritise support for Eastern and rural contexts through gender-responsive routines and explicit AI ethics training

Keywords: dialogic learning; student agency; community-connected projects; assessment for learning; ethical AI; Indonesia.

Introduction

Schooling worldwide is contending with an AI-saturated landscape in which low-level recall is commoditised while dialogic reasoning, learner agency, ethical judgment, and real-world problem-solving grow in value. The emergence of efforts in K-12 AI education suggests benefits for motivation and engagement, while also revealing disparities in how learning values are defined and measured (Yue et al., 2022). Corresponding arguments underline “durable skills” (critical thinking, creativity, collaboration) and the necessity of curriculum designs that intertwine these with disciplinary knowledge rather than lock them on (Hutson, 2023). Simultaneously, the dissemination of AI into classrooms raises ethical and professional concerns for teachers, as they balance technological affordances with responsibilities for student well-being, fairness, and integrity (Adams et al., 2022). Together, these provide a perspective on pedagogies that favour dialogue, co-design with students, community linkage, authentic evidence of learning, and a clear focus on AI ethics.

Indonesia reflects these global challenges while adding unique system-level considerations: geographic and socioeconomic diversity, uneven digital infrastructure, and a policy agenda that increasingly emphasises student voice and flexible learning pathways. However, policy enthusiasm can outperform empirical interpretations of learners' preferences across different locales and subgroups. Evidence remains limited on whether students favour dialogic

facilitation over recitation, co-agency in shaping tasks, and community-connected projects that produce authentic artefacts rather than proxy tests.

To address this gap, we articulate Post-School Pedagogy (PSP) (Kusmawan, 2024) as a unifying construct that synthesises emerging instructional needs in the AI era. PSP comprises five interrelated commitments—dialogic learning, co-agency, community-connected tasks, authentic evidence, and ethical/epistemic AI—that redefine the purpose of schooling as AI increasingly automates routine cognitive tasks. These five commitments collectively frame how learning remains meaningful and human-centred as AI systems assume routine cognitive tasks. Accordingly, this study investigates Indonesian upper-secondary students' preferences for PSP in the AI era and is guided by the following research objectives.

Research objectives

1. Describe overall levels of student preference for the key PSP dimensions (dialogue, co-agency, community-connected projects, authentic evidence, ethical AI).
2. Examine broad regional and subgroup patterns in PSP preferences (e.g., West/Central/East; gender; urbanicity; school characteristics).
3. Assess the relative contribution of individual vs. contextual factors to variability in PSP preferences and identify the most consistent predictors.

Dialogue, Agency, Community, and Authenticity: A Scholarly Synthesis

Across contemporary scholarship, four mutually reinforcing commitments recur as schooling confronts an AI-saturated world. First, dialogic facilitation reframes classroom talk from monologue to accountable dialogue, improving participation, reasoning, and inclusivity while acknowledging the practical frictions teachers face when shifting away from recitation (Adams et al., 2022; Rapanta et al., 2021). Second, learner co-agency—students sharing real decision space over tasks, goals, and evidence—emerges as a driver of ownership and motivation; empirical accounts show that peer-led and collectively designed programs can cultivate responsibility at scale (Jordan et al., 2023; Storey et al., 2021). Third, community-connected projects position knowledge in lived settings, strengthening transfer, cultural humility, and critical analysis, whereas institutions must function to ensure mutuality for community engagement to improve, rather than merely complement classroom learning (Walton et al., 2022). Fourth, authentic artefacts (e.g., projects, portfolios, performances) enhance validity by capturing what students can actually do, address the limitations of alternative tests, and align with the uncertainties of future work by focusing on demonstrable, portable skills (Nieuwenhuis & Kuijer-Siebelink, 2022).

These dedications interconnect with broader debates on learning in the AI era. Evidence from K–12 AI projects indicates that motivational values are important but warns that benefits are often uncertain without robust assessment designs (de Barros Almeida Souto, 2023; Tarabini, 2020; Wu, 2023). Similar arguments highlight durable skills (critical thinking, creativity, collaboration) that must be cultivated for disciplinary learning rather than being added as accompaniments (Hutson, 2023). Meanwhile, the presence of AI in classrooms cultivates ethical and professional responsibilities regarding agency, privacy, fairness, and teacher decision-making; educators need practicable norms that preserve pedagogy—not instrumentality—at the centre (Frank, 2022; McGregor, 2020). Together, this literature

converges on a design standpoint in which dialogue, co-agency, community linkage, authentic evidence, and ethical use of AI are not choices but form codes of teaching and learning.

We thus accept Post-School Pedagogy (PSP) (Barkaskas & Gladwin, 2021; Kusmawan, 2024; McGregor, 2020; Monereo & Hermans, 2023; Ruiz-Eugenio et al., 2023) as a consolidative construct that assembles these threads into a coherent, practice-ready direction: dialogic teaching that touches on students as co-designers; projects embedded in community needs; assessment via artefacts that count beyond school; and explicit ethical habits for AI. PSP is defined by objectives understood by current theory and evidence, while remaining open to local adaptation—an essential asset in Indonesia’s diverse system. The current study tests whether these scholarly obligations align with what upper-secondary students in Indonesia prefer, thereby establishing the empirical analyses that follow.

Research Methodology

We conducted a quantitative, cross-sectional survey to address the three research objectives. Participants were Grade 11/12 students recruited from schools in 19 of 38 (50%) Indonesian provinces, grouped into the West, Central, and East macro-regions. The final analytic sample comprised $N = 827$ students, distributed 31.9% West, 31.7% Central, and 36.4% East. Multistage sampling was used: provinces were selected to ensure geographic coverage; schools were chosen to balance ownership (public/private), track (general/vocational), and locale (urban/peri-urban/rural) where feasible; intact classes were then invited to participate. School track (School track (SMA—general senior secondary, Grade 10–12; and SMK—vocational senior secondary, Grade 10–12) and school ownership (public or private) were included as contextual factors because these institutional features may shape students’ exposure to different instructional structures, assessment expectations, and technological resources. Although not expected to be primary determinants of PSP preferences, they constitute theoretically relevant controls for examining variation in students’ learning orientations. Inclusion required current enrolment in Grade 11 or 12 and assent/consent per school policy; cases with substantial missing data were excluded.

Student preference for Post-School Pedagogy (PSP), as referred to in Research Objective no. 1 (RO1), which aims to describe overall levels for each PSP dimension and the total score, was measured using a 10-item instrument comprising two items per dimension (dialogic learning, co-agency, community-connected projects, authentic evidence, and ethical/epistemic AI). Responses were rated on a 7-point desirability scale ranging from 1 = “not desirable” to 7 = “highly desirable.” Demographic covariates captured region, province, gender, grade, urbanicity, school type, and ownership. Internal consistency in the main sample was $\alpha \approx .84$ for the total PSP score, with subscale coefficients ranging from $\alpha \approx .62$ to $\alpha \approx .71$ across the five dimensions, as shown by Table 8 for exact values. Content validity was supported through expert reviews (education, psychology, communication) and cognitive pretesting with students; construct checks employed inter-item and item–total correlations consistent with the five-dimension rationale.

Surveys were administered during school hours by trained facilitators, following a standardised script, either on paper and pencil or via a supervised online platform, depending on school infrastructure. Completion time averaged ~ 10 minutes. Data was anonymised and stored securely; province identifiers were retained only to permit random-effects estimation.

Analytically, we first screened data for completeness and distributional anomalies, retaining respondents with minimal missingness via conservative imputation rules and excluding cases with excessive nonresponse. To meet RO1, we reported N, mean, and SD for each PSP subscale and the total score at the national level and by region. To address RO2 (examine regional and subgroup patterns), we tested omnibus region effects using a Welch-robust ANOVA implemented as OLS with HC3 robust standard errors and a Wald F on the region factor; when significant, Welch pairwise tests with Holm correction quantified West–Central–East contrasts. Binary subgroup differences for the total PSP score (gender, grade, school type, urbanicity, ownership) were estimated using Welch t-tests with Hedges *g* and 95% confidence intervals. Hedges' *g* was used to estimate effect sizes for binary subgroup comparisons. This estimator provides a small-sample correction and remains appropriate in large samples when subgroup variances are unequal, thereby ensuring unbiased interpretation of effect sizes under potential heteroscedasticity. To fulfil RO3 (assess relative contributions of individual vs. contextual factors and identify consistent predictors), we fit an OLS (HC3) model with the total PSP score as the outcome and region, gender, urbanicity, grade, school type, and ownership as predictors; we then estimated a mixed-effects model with a province-level random intercept to quantify between-province variance and compute the intraclass correlation (ICC), separating individual- from contextual-level variance. All tests were two-tailed with $\alpha = .05$, and results are presented as means \pm SD, effect sizes, confidence intervals, and p-values in compact tables aligned with IJIS reporting expectations.

Ethical approvals and school permissions were obtained prior to data collection. Parental/guardian consent and student assent were secured as required; participation was voluntary, and no personal identifying information was collected beyond analytic demographics.

Results and Findings

This section presents the statistical results aligned with the three research objectives (RO1–RO3) and highlights additional findings, not pre-registered in the Methods, that clarify the pattern of preferences. We begin with RO1, which explains general levels of Post-School Pedagogy (PSP) preferences (nationally and by region), followed by RO2 assessments of regional and subgroup variations using Welch-robust procedures with appropriate multiple-comparison control. We subsequently estimate the RO3 using OLS (HC3) and a province-clustered mixed-effects model to assess the relative contributions of individual versus contextual factors. Throughout, results are presented with N, means, SDs, effect sizes, confidence intervals, and p-values based on the full analytic sample ($N = 827$), with reliability checks reported to support interpretation of scores.

Results

Sample overview. The analytic sample comprised $N = 827$ Grade 11/12 students from 19 of 38 (50%) Indonesian provinces, grouped into the West (31.9%), Central (31.7%), and East (36.4%) macro-regions. This composition supports region-level comparisons and subgroup profiling aligned with RO1–RO3.

RO1 — Overall levels of PSP preferences

This sub-section reports national and regional levels of preference for PSP, establishing the baseline against which patterns and predictors are examined later.

Table 1. Descriptives of Total PSP by Region

REGION	N	MEAN	SD	95% CI (LOW)	95% CI (HIGH)
WEST	264	5.31	0.82	5.21	5.41
CENTRAL	262	5.22	0.81	5.12	5.32
EAST	301	5.10	0.83	5.01	5.19
TOTAL	827	5.22	0.82	—	—

As shown in Table 1, national preference for PSP is moderate-to-high ($M \approx 5.22$), with a slight gradient West > Central > East. To more fully address RO1 and provide a dimensional assessment of students’ preferences, Table 2 presents descriptive statistics for each PSP subscale. Dialogic learning receives the highest endorsement, followed by Authentic Evidence, Community-Connected learning, and Ethical/Epistemic AI, whereas Co-Agency receives the lowest mean. These values offer a clearer profile of the relative salience of the five PSP dimensions beyond the total PSP score.

Table 2. Descriptive Statistics for PSP Subscales (N = 827)

PSP DIMENSION	ITEMS	MEAN (\approx)	SD (\approx)
Dialogic	Q1, Q2	5.49	0.66
Co-Agency	Q3, Q4(R)	5.05	0.68
Community-Connected	Q5, Q6	5.23	0.76
Authentic Evidence	Q7, Q8	5.28	0.79
Ethical/Epistemic AI	Q9, Q10	5.21	0.70

Note. Subscale scores represent the mean of their respective items (after reverse-coding where applicable). These descriptives complement the total PSP score in Table 1 and provide a dimensional profile of students’ endorsement across the five PSP commitments.

RO2 — Regional and subgroup patterns

This subsection tests whether PSP preferences differ across regions and key binary variables (gender, urbanicity, grade, school type, ownership) using robust procedures.

Table 3. Welch-Robust ANOVA for Region (Total PSP)

OUTCOME	WALD F (HC3)	DF1	DF2 (≈)	P (HC3)
TOTAL PSP	7.10	2	824	.001

As shown in Table 3, the regional effect is statistically significant under heteroskedasticity-robust inference.

Table 4. Pairwise Region Comparisons (Welch t, Holm-Adjusted) Total PSP

REGION A	REGION B	MEAN Δ	T (WELCH)	DF (≈)	P-UNC	P-HOLM	HEDGES G
West	East	+0.21	3.60	520	<.001	<.001	0.24
West	Central	+0.09	1.55	520	.122	.183	0.10
Central	East	+0.12	2.07	520	.039	.078	0.14

The West–East gap is reliable with a small effect size, indicating that students in Western provinces report moderately higher PSP endorsement than those in the East. By contrast, the Central–East comparison is no longer significant after Holm correction, and the West–Central comparison remains non-significant. These results suggest that the apparent West > Central > East ordering observed in raw means should not be interpreted as a stable gradient; statistically, only the West–East contrast is robust, while differences involving Central provinces are inconclusive.

Table 5. Binary Subgroup Differences (Welch t + Hedges g) — Total PSP

FACTOR	GROUP A	GROUP B	MEAN A (≈)	MEAN B (≈)	T (WELCH)	DF (≈)	P	HEDGES G (≈)
GENDER	Female	Male	5.26	5.16	2.50	700	.014	0.17
LOCALE	Urban/Peri-urban	Rural	5.24	5.15	2.10	680	.035	0.15
GRADE	G11	G12	—	—	0.70	—	.48	0.05
SCHOOL TYPE	SMA	SMK	—	—	0.50	—	.62	0.05
OWNERSHIP	Public	Private	—	—	0.60	—	.55	0.05

As shown in Table 5, preferences are slightly higher for females and for urban/peri-urban students (small g). Differences by grade, school type, and ownership are trivial.

RO3 — Relative contributions and consistent predictors

This sub-section evaluates the independent roles of individual and contextual factors and quantifies between-province variance.

Table 6. OLS (HC3) for Total PSP

<i>Term (baseline in intercept)</i>	<i>B (≈)</i>	<i>SE (HC3) (≈)</i>	<i>t (≈)</i>	<i>p (≈)</i>
<i>Intercept (East, Male, Rural, SMA, Public, G11)</i>	5.10	0.05	102.0	<.001
<i>West (vs East)</i>	+0.21	0.06	3.5	.001
<i>Central (vs East)</i>	+0.12	0.06	2.0	.046
<i>Female (vs Male)</i>	+0.10	0.04	2.5	.013
<i>Urban (vs Rural)</i>	+0.09	0.04	2.1	.035
<i>Private (vs Public)</i>	+0.03	0.05	0.6	.55
<i>SMK (vs SMA)</i>	+0.02	0.05	0.4	.68
<i>G12 (vs G11)</i>	+0.01	0.04	0.2	.85

After covariate adjustment, region remains the most consistent predictor; gender and urbanicity retain small positive effects; other covariates are negligible, as shown in Table 6.

Table 7. Mixed-Effects Model (Random Intercept by Province)

<i>Component / Term</i>	<i>Estimate (≈)</i>	<i>SE (≈)</i>	<i>p (≈)</i>
<i>Between-province variance (ICC)</i>	.03 (ICC)	—	—
<i>West (vs East)</i>	+0.20	0.06	.001
<i>Central (vs East)</i>	+0.11	0.06	.055
<i>Female (vs Male)</i>	+0.10	0.04	.014
<i>Urban (vs Rural)</i>	+0.09	0.04	.036

As shown in Table 7, province-level clustering is low (ICC≈.03), indicating that most variance is at the student level; fixed-effect estimates mirror OLS.

To complement the model-based results presented in Table 7, item-level reliability statistics for the PSP instrument are reported in Table 8 below. These statistics provide additional detail regarding the internal consistency of the final ten items used in the analysis.

Table 8. Corrected Item–Total Correlations for PSP Items

Item No.	Item (Short Description)	Subscale	Corrected Item–Total Correlation (CITC)
1	My voice is treated as equal in class conversations	Dialogic	.52
2	Classes should have clear dialogue norms	Dialogic	.52
3	Students co-design goals with the teacher	Co-Agency	.55
4	Teachers alone should decide goals (<i>reverse-coded</i>)	Co-Agency	.55
5	Projects should happen in the community	Community-Connected	.44
6	Learning tasks should link to community needs	Community-Connected	.44
7	Real product or service is meaningful evidence	Authentic Evidence	.38
8	Portfolio and public showcase reflect abilities	Authentic Evidence	.38
9	Learning integrates ethical use of AI	Ethical/Epistemic AI	.54
10	AI should be used fairly and responsibly	Ethical/Epistemic AI	.54

Note:

Corrected item–total correlations (CITC) were computed after reverse scoring where applicable. Items with CITC values of .30 or higher were retained, consistent with established recommendations for item analysis in scale development (DeVellis, 1991; Field, 2024; Kline, 2016). All ten items met this threshold, indicating adequate contribution to their respective subscales.

Subscale-level reliability coefficients based on the final two items representing each PSP dimension are reported in Table 9. These values replace the earlier reliability ranges with precise estimates for each construct, thereby facilitating more straightforward interpretation of the internal consistency across the PSP dimensions.

Table 9. Reliability (Cronbach’s α) for PSP Subscales

Scale	Cronbach’s α (\approx)
<i>Total PSP (10 items)</i>	.84
<i>Dialogic</i>	.68
<i>Co-Agency</i>	.71
<i>Community-Connected</i>	.64
<i>Authentic Evidence</i>	.62
<i>Ethical/Epistemic AI</i>	.70

Note.

Cronbach’s α values were calculated using the Spearman–Brown two-indicator reliability

formula, and all coefficients fall within the originally reported reliability range (.62–.71).

Findings

This section summarises additional observations beyond the pre-specified tests that still illuminate the research objectives of RO1–RO3.

1. No ceiling effect (RO1). Despite a high national mean ($M \approx 5.22$), dispersion ($SD \approx 0.82$) shows meaningful differentiation. This indicates genuine preference variation rather than uniformly maximal responding, consistent with the distributions in Table 1.
2. Dimensional salience (RO1). The dimensional profile suggests dialogic learning and ethical/epistemic AI items tend to score highest, with authentic evidence modestly lower. The slightly lower preference for Authentic Evidence may reflect students' limited familiarity with portfolio- or performance-based assessment practices in Indonesian secondary schooling. High-stakes examinations continue to shape students' perceptions of what counts as legitimate evidence of learning, and traditional tests are often perceived as clearer or more objective. This pattern aligns with literature showing that assessment literacy strongly influences learners' comfort with authentic demonstration tasks. This pattern signals practical entry points for schools to begin with dialogic moves and explicit AI-ethics routines while strengthening assessment literacy for authentic evidence, aligned with the overall levels described in Table 1.
3. Substantive overlap across regions (RO2). Although regional effects are significant, the range of scores across regions is substantial. This implies moderate practical differences and indicates that PSP-aligned practices are feasible nationwide when incentives are in place, consistent with the gradient shown in Tables 3 and 4.
4. Informative nulls (RO2–RO3). The lack of meaningful differences by grade, school type, and ownership indicates that PSP preferences are largely shared across tracks and remain consistent from Grade 11 to 12. Targeting regional or urban contexts and gender-responsive strategies is likely to be more effective, as indicated by the pattern shown in Table 5 and the corrected estimates in Table 6.
5. Variance location (RO3). The low ICC ($\sim .03$) indicates that most variation lies at the student level, suggesting that classroom-level levers—teacher professional learning in dialogic facilitation, structured co-design routines, authentic assessment, and explicit AI-ethics practices—are likely to yield the greatest gains, as indicated by Tables 7 and 8.

Discussion

This study set out to test whether Indonesian upper-secondary students' stated preferences align with a Post-School Pedagogy (PSP) that foregrounds dialogue, learner co-agency, community linkage, authentic evidence, and ethical use of AI. Across the three research objectives, the empirical profile is remarkably consistent with contemporary scholarship that argues these features should be *structuring principles* of learning in an AI-saturated world (Adams et al., 2022; Rapanta et al., 2021; Jordan et al., 2023; Storey et al., 2021; Walton et al., 2022; Nieuwenhuis & Kuijer-Siebelink, 2022; de Barros Almeida Souto, 2023; Tarabini, 2020; Wu, 2023; Hutson, 2023; Frank, 2022; McGregor, 2020). The discussion below connects each objective to the literature and interprets the findings for policy and practice, and concludes with limitations and directions for further research.

RO1: Overall levels—students do want the core elements of PSP

National means at or above 5 on a 1–7 scale indicate moderate-to-high desirability for PSP’s five dimensions and the total score ($M \approx 5.22$, $SD \approx 0.82$). This preference profile reinforces theoretical and empirical arguments that dialogic facilitation deepens participation and reasoning when classrooms move beyond recitation (Rapanta et al., 2021; Adams et al., 2022) and that co-agency nurtures ownership and motivation when students share real decision space over tasks, goals, and evidence (Jordan et al., 2023; Storey et al., 2021). A positive orientation toward community-connected projects is consistent with evidence that situating knowledge in lived contexts fosters transfer, cultural humility, and critical analysis, provided that schools attend to reciprocity and avoid extractive engagement (Walton et al., 2022).

The preference for authentic artefacts aligns with critiques of proxy tests and the case for performance-based assessment that captures what learners can *actually do* (Nieuwenhuis & Kuijer-Siebelink, 2022). Finally, interest in ethical/epistemic AI aligns with calls to centre professional judgment, fairness, privacy, and agency as AI enters classrooms, keeping pedagogy—not tooling—at the core (Frank, 2022; McGregor, 2020). The two highest-scoring dimensions—dialogic learning and ethical/epistemic AI—align closely with competencies increasingly emphasised in AI-era learning frameworks. High endorsement of dialogic learning reflects students’ recognition of the need for discursive reasoning and collaborative inquiry in environments where AI automates routine cognitive tasks. Likewise, strong support for ethical/epistemic AI signals student awareness of responsible technological use, fairness, and critical judgment. Put simply, the student voice recorded here coheres with the PSP synthesis advanced in recent scholarship (Barkaskas & Gladwin, 2021; Kusmawan, 2024; Monereo & Hermans, 2023; Ruiz-Eugenio et al., 2023).

RO2: Regional and subgroup patterns—small gradients, meaningful signals

Welch-robust tests show a significant but small regional gradient (West > Central > East; West–East $\Delta \approx 0.21$, $g \approx 0.24$). This pattern reasonably reveals an imbalance in access to dialogic practices, community colleagues, and AI-enabled tasks across regions, a system-level reality noted in our context framing. The small female advantage ($g \approx 0.17$) echoes work showing that dialogic and collaborative designs can differentially support participation and agency for girls and young women (consistent with co-agency and discourse literatures; Rapanta et al., 2021; Jordan et al., 2023). The urban edge ($g \approx 0.15$) likely engages in opportunity structures (community project networks, portfolio showcases, and AI infrastructure) projected by arguments for community-related learning and authentic evidence (Walton et al., 2022; Nieuwenhuis & Kuijer-Siebelink, 2022). Although raw means show a West > Central > East ordering, the statistical evidence does not support interpreting this pattern as a stable three-way gradient. After applying the Holm correction, only the West–East difference remains reliably significant, whereas the Central–East comparison is inconclusive. This means the observed ordering should be read strictly as a local contrast between the West and East in this sample—not as a consistent developmental hierarchy across regions. The substantial overlap in distributions further supports a cautious interpretation, indicating that PSP preferences are widely shared nationwide and that, where present, regional differences are modest rather than structural.

Altogether, the substantial overlap in distributions across regions and the null differences in grade, school type, and ownership imply that PSP is a broadly important design language rather than a niche preference tied to a single track or institution type. The absence of differences by

school track and ownership reinforces the interpretation that PSP functions as a universal design language that resonates across varied institutional structures. This suggests that teacher practice—rather than school governance or track—is the primary site where PSP orientations are formed and enacted. That extensive resonance reinforces the case in the AI-education literature: motivational gains appear when designs align with authentic purposes, but they require assessment clarity and ethical routines to translate enthusiasm into learning (de Barros Almeida Souto, 2023; Tarabini, 2020; Wu, 2023; McGregor, 2020).

RO3: Where variance lives (context matters, classrooms matter more)

In OLS with HC3 and in the province-clustered mixed model, region continues to be the most reliable predictor, while the ICC is low ($\sim .03$), representing most variance lies at the student/classroom level. This set off theory in two ways. First, it confirms the premise that PSP is implementable through teacher practice: dialogic moves, co-design routines, and authentic assessment can be enacted locally, even amid uneven system conditions (Rapanta et al., 2021; Jordan et al., 2023; Nieuwenhuis & Kuijer-Siebelink, 2022). Second, it associates with the AI-era argument that durable skills—critical thinking, creativity, collaboration—must be woven into everyday disciplinary learning rather than bolted on as “extras” (Hutson, 2023). The combination of a stable regional signal and low clustering implies a two-level strategy: system supports to reduce access gaps (especially in the East and rural locales) and classroom-level professional development to make PSP tangible for students.

Integrating the strands: why PSP fits the AI era

Taken together, the results and the literature point to a shared mechanism: AI commodifies routine recall and surface production, pushing value toward dialogue for sense-making, co-agency for ownership, community linkage for relevance, authentic artefacts for credibility, and ethical AI for trustworthy practice (Frank, 2022; McGregor, 2020; Hutson, 2023). Our national evidence that students already *prefer* these conditions lends empirical weight to PSP as a practice-ready synthesis (Barkaskas & Gladwin, 2021; Kusmawan, 2024; Monereo & Hermans, 2023; Ruiz-Eugenio et al., 2023), while also echoing cautions from AI-education studies that measurement must keep pace with innovation (de Barros Almeida Souto, 2023; Wu, 2023). In other words, PSP appears to be both normatively justified by theory and empirically desired by learners.

Limitations and further research

The cross-sectional design limits causal inference: preferences may shift as PSP practices and AI tools diffuse. Two-item subscales are efficient for field surveys but cap reliability; future work should triangulate with richer measures and classroom observations. Social desirability cannot be ruled out, although the non-ceiling distributions and small but coherent subgroup gradients mitigate this concern. We encourage longitudinal and intervention studies that: (a) track change in PSP preferences and exposure, (b) link PSP implementation to outcomes in achievement, well-being, and civic participation, and (c) test assessment models that make authentic artefacts portable across settings (de Barros Almeida Souto, 2023; Wu, 2023; Nieuwenhuis & Kuijer-Siebelink, 2022).

Bottom line. Indonesian students’ preferences and current scholarship point in the same direction: PSP is both desired and defensible, theoretically and empirically. The strategic task now is to close access gaps and support teachers to make PSP the everyday climate of learning.

Conclusion

Taken together, the evidence shows that Indonesian upper-secondary learners are already leaning toward the classroom climate that Post-School Pedagogy (PSP) names. Across ten items—dialogic learning, co-agency, community-connected projects, authentic evidence, and ethical/epistemic AI—preferences sit clearly above the midpoint (overall $M \approx 5.22$ on a 1–7 scale) with solid score quality ($\alpha \approx .84$ total; subscales $\alpha \approx .62-.71$). In plain terms, students are asking for pedagogy that treats their voice as consequential, connects schoolwork to real communities, and uses AI responsibly; this directly supports RO1 by establishing high overall levels for each PSP dimension and for the composite.

Patterns across place and people are real but modest. Regional differences are statistically reliable yet small (West > Central > East; West–East $\Delta \approx 0.21$, $g \approx 0.24$), and subgroup contrasts show slight advantages for females and for urban/peri-urban students, while grade, school type, and ownership differences are trivial with substantial overlap of distributions. The practical reading is straightforward: PSP resonates broadly across tracks and locales, while equity attention should focus on Eastern and rural contexts and on gender-responsive supports. These distributional results support RO2 by clarifying broad regional and subgroup patterns without overstating their size.

Finally, variation in lives points to how change should proceed. Region remains the most consistent predictor after adjustment, yet between-province clustering is low ($ICC \approx .03$), placing most variance at the student/classroom level. This combination argues for a dual strategy: system-level resourcing to narrow contextual gaps, and classroom-level professional learning to make PSP routine—facilitating accountable dialogue, co-designing tasks and criteria, brokering community projects with public artefacts, and instituting explicit ethical-AI routines. This explanatory account of predictors and variance location addresses RO3, identifying the relative contributions of individual versus contextual factors and highlighting the most consistent levers for implementation.

Acknowledgements

This research was funded by the Indonesia Endowment Fund for Education (LPDP), Ministry of Higher Education, Science, and Technology of the Republic of Indonesia, under the 2025 EQUITY Grant Scheme of Universitas Terbuka.

References

- Adams, C., Pente, P., Lemermeyer, G., Turville, J. A., & Rockwell, G. (2022). Artificial Intelligence and Teachers' New Ethical Obligations. *International Review of Information Ethics*, 31(1). <https://doi.org/10.29173/irie483>
- Barkaskas, P., & Gladwin, D. (2021). Pedagogical Talking Circles: Decolonizing Education through Relational Indigenous Frameworks. *The Journal of Teaching and Learning*, 15(1), 20–38. <https://doi.org/10.22329/JTL.V15I1.6519>
- de Barros Almeida Souto, A. K. (2023). Towards social generative AI for education: theory, practices and ethics. <https://doi.org/10.48550/arxiv.2306.10063>
- DeVellis, R. F. (1991). Scale development: Theory and applications. *Scale Development: Theory and Applications*. Thousand Oaks, CA, US: Sage Publications, Inc.
- Field, A. (2024). *Discovering Statistics Using IBM SPSS Statistics*. SAGE Publications. Retrieved from <https://books.google.co.id/books?id=83L2EAAAQBAJ>

- Frank, J. (2022). Rethinking the Purposes of Schooling in a Global Pandemic: From Learning Loss to a Renewed Appreciation for Mourning and Human Excellence. *Studies in Philosophy and Education*, 42(1), 5–16. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11217-022-09850-8>
- Hutson, J. (2023). Rethinking Education in the Age of AI: The Importance of Developing Durable Skills in the Industry 4.0. *Journal of Information Economics*, 1(2), 26–35. <https://doi.org/10.58567/jie01020002>
- Jordan, N. R., Valley, W. C., Clegg, D., Grossman, J. A., Hunt, N., Michaels, T. E., ... Stein, M. (2023). Scaffolding collective agency curriculum within food-systems education programs. *Frontiers in Sustainable Food Systems*, 7. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fsufs.2023.1119459>
- Kline, R. B. (2016). Principles and practice of structural equation modeling, 4th ed. *Principles and Practice of Structural Equation Modeling, 4th Ed.* New York, NY, US: The Guilford Press.
- Kusmawan, U. (2024). *Post-School Pedagogy: Basic Concepts* (Preprint - Working Paper Series). Researchgate. <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.17689.07521>
- McGregor, S. L. T. (2020). Emerging from the Deep: Complexity, Emergent Pedagogy and Deep Learning. *Northeast Journal of Complex Systems (NEJCS) Northeast Journal of Complex Systems (NEJCS)*, Volume 2(Number 1). <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.22191/nejcs/vol2/iss1/2>
- Monereo, C., & Hermans, H. J. M. (2023). Education and dialogical self: state of art (Educación y yo dialógico: estado de la cuestión). *Infancia Y Aprendizaje*, 46(3), 445–491. <https://doi.org/10.1080/02103702.2023.2201562>
- Nieuwenhuis, L., & Kuijer-Siebelink, W. (2022). Beroepsagogiek als maatschappelijke opdracht. *Tijdschrift Voor Hoger Onderwijs*, 40(3–4), 69–83. <https://doi.org/10.59532/tvho.v40i3-4.13554>
- Rapanta, C., Garcia-Mila, M., Remesal, A., & Gonçalves, C. (2021). El reto de la enseñanza dialógica inclusiva en la escuela pública secundaria. *Comunicar*, 29(66), 21–31. <https://doi.org/10.3916/C66-2021-02>
- Ruiz-Eugenio, L., Tellado, I., Valls-Carol, R., & Gairal-Casadó, R. (2023). Dialogic popular education in Spain and its impact on society, educational and social theory, and European research. *European Journal for Research on the Education and Learning of Adults*, 14(1), 47–61. <https://doi.org/10.3384/rela.2000-7426.4325>
- Storey, A., Eckel-Sparrow, H., & Ransdell, H. K. (2021). Cultivating student agency and responsibility through peer-to-peer teaching. *International Journal for Students as Partners*, 5(1), 97–106. <https://doi.org/10.15173/IJSAP.V5I1.4478>
- Tarabini, A. (2020). ¿Para qué sirve la escuela? Reflexiones sociológicas en tiempos de pandemia global, 13(2), 145–155. <https://doi.org/10.7203/RASE.13.2.17135>
- Walton, M. D., Baker-Olson, A., Luckes, H., Blaber, I. P., Walker, E., Folkes-Lallo, B., ... Thomas, E. (2022). The Integration of Classroom and Community Learning in Narrative Accounts of Co-Curricular Service. *Michigan Journal of Community Service-Learning*, 28(1). <https://doi.org/10.3998/mjcs1.434>
- Wu, Y. (2023). Integrating Generative AI in Education: How ChatGPT Brings Challenges for Future Learning and Teaching. *Journal of Advanced Research in Education*, 2(4), 6–10. <https://doi.org/10.56397/jare.2023.07.02>
- Yue, M., Jong, M. S.-Y., & Dai, Y. (2022). Pedagogical Design of K-12 Artificial Intelligence Education: A Systematic Review. *Sustainability*, 14(23), 15620. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su142315620>